

Effect of local bodies of water on organic matter decomposition in an environment

Aim:

The aim of this research is to investigate the effect of local bodies of water on the decomposition of organic matter in the surrounding environment. Specifically, this research aims to explore how the different locations of these bodies of water, and their characteristics, including pH, temperature, nutrients, and salinity, affect the rate of organic matter decomposition.

Questions:

1. How does the rate of organic matter decomposition vary across different locations in local bodies of water - according to water body type, size, altitude?
2. What is the relationship between water temperature and organic matter decomposition rates?
3. What is the relationship between water salinity and organic matter decomposition rates?
4. What is the relationship between water pH and organic matter decomposition rates?
5. What is the relationship between water conductivity and organic matter decomposition rates?
6. What role do nutrient concentrations (nitrogen, phosphorus, Salinity) play in organic matter decomposition rates?

Hypotheses:

In the experiment, the fact that the green tea contains simpler compounds than rooibos tea, we are likely to have the green tea bag decompose faster than the rooibos tea bag in all locations tested. This will be reflected in a greater weight loss for the green tea bag compared to the rooibos tea bag over the same time period. Additionally, the rate of decomposition will vary between locations due to differences in environmental factors such as pH, temperature, and nutrient availability. And we can predict that the tea bags will decompose more rapidly in locations with higher temperatures and nutrient concentrations, and that non-neutral pH may have a negative effect on decomposition rates.

Methods:

1. Selection of the study sites:

A minimum of six bodies of water will be selected to have a more accurate comparison and representation. The bodies of water will be selected based on their environmental conditions, including temperature, salinity, nutrient levels, and other relevant factors. The study sites will include both natural and human-modified bodies of water as well as still lakes and small flowing rivers.

2. Preparation of tea bags:

Two types of tea bags, green tea, and rooibos tea, will be used in the study. 20 tea bags of each type will be purchased from the same company with the same weight and tea bag shape to ensure a fair comparison. The tea bags will be weighed before they are transported to experimentation location to track changes in weight during the experiment.

3. Setting up of tea bags:

Two tea bags of each type will be anchored to the ground at each study site at a depth of approximately 10 cm below the water surface. The tea bags will be attached to a string for retrieval after three months.

4. Environmental measurements:

The set up should be completed within one week to ensure bags are exposed across the same seasons and to allow fair comparison of environmental conditions. At the start of the experiment local environmental conditions will be assessed using a testing kit to measure temperature, salinity, pH, nitrogen, phosphorus, and other relevant parameters (water surface tension as an indicator of water pollution levels). I will record exact location coordinates and altitudes using an iPhone app and take photos of each study site. All the measurements will be recorded in a logbook and spreadsheet for later analysis.

5. Retrieval of tea bags:

After three months, the tea bags will be retrieved from each study site. The tea bags will be handled carefully to avoid any damage. The tea bags will then be cleaned externally from debris and dried at room temperature for 48 hours and weighed. The weight will be used to calculate organic mass loss by a comparison of the original tea bag weight to the current weight.

6. Measurement and analysis:

The weight of the tea bags will be analyzed to determine the rate of decomposition. The percentage weight loss of each tea bag will be calculated using the initial and final weights. The data will be analyzed using statistical regression techniques to determine the factors (pH, salinity, temp, nitrogen and phosphorus) that I expect will affect decomposition the most.

Equipment:

- Rooibos tea
- Green tea
- Plastic string
- Sellotape
- Permanent marker
- Electric scale (accurate to 0.01 grams)
- Digging tools
- Trays for weighing
- Brush
- Scissors
- Phone
- Apps for determining location using GPS and water surface tension
- Thermometer
- Water testing kit
- Gloves
- Gumboots